

M20: Mid-project review of user engagement and impact on prediction system developments

Date: 30.12.2024.

Funded by
the European Union

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USER ENGAGEMENT

- background -

User engagement

Objective 5

Explore for the first time how users can get value from considering information on seasonal / 1-5-year / 5-30-year time scales together to improve decision-making.

Identification of Super Users' needs for seamless climate information.

Guiding the work of the project technical WPs.

Co-development of prototype climate services with Super Users.

Interactions through interviews, meetings and participation in User Forums.

Assessment of climate information use and user needs across Europe

Conducting literature review, quantitative surveying, analysis of user databases, engagement with users through User Forums, to inform developments across ASPECT.

Organise annual multi-sector User Forums

Facilitate user engagement beyond the Super Users by convening annual multi-sector User Forums to create a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users of climate information

User engagement strategy

User engagement refers to how the consortium interacts with potential users of seamless climate information both within (i.e. across WPs and with Super Users) and outside the ASPECT consortium.

- **Internal user community:** project partners + Super Users collaboratively developing prototype climate services using S2D predictions and projections.
- **Community of practice:** users that know what to do and start to build capacity to be able to create and/or use climate services with S2D prediction information. Expected to be a legacy of ASPECT.
- **Community of interest:** individuals that are aware of and desire to use S2D predictions either directly or through climate service provider.

User engagement model

User Engagement Model

- defines internal & external user interaction
- should help ASPECT devise strategies that enhance user interactions and fosters the development of robust communities of practice for upscaling of project outputs

User Engagement Committee

- composed of representatives of all WPs
- established to enhance internal interaction in order to better engage with external users

ASPECT goals within this context:

- to build or strengthen a community of interest around seamless climate information, thereby expanding the reach and impact of ASPECT work
- to evolve community of interest into fully-fledged communities of practice in the long run, which should be 'self sustained' and capable of using and exploiting the project's results

User engagement model

Range of ASPECT “Users”

Super Users in ASPECT

Organisations working closely with researchers to co-produce climate information spanning from seasons to decades and cutting across different time scales, which can help make better informed decisions for adaptation

MEET THE TEAM

Climate is an important factor in wine production, with climate change rising on the agenda. ASPECT will provide information on long-term and short-term variability of water availability over the coming decades and years, helping Codorniu make decisions to adapt to climate variability and change.

Asi Borde
 Director, Research & Innovation
 ASPECT Super User

MEET THE TEAM

Climate change can impact a wide range of people and organisations. ASPECT provides the improved climate information for better informed decisions on how to adapt to the risks of climate change, including investment decision making.

Professor Ian Cleverly
 Professor of Economics
 Director of the Centre for Climate Change Research
 ASPECT Super User

MEET THE TEAM

The EU Mission on Adaptation to climate change helps regions and territories to better adapt to climate change. Strategic support from ASPECT is helping the Emilia-Romagna Region to improve its adaptation to climate change, including the development of a regional adaptation plan.

Giulia Assarelli
 Head of the Mission for Climate Adaptation
 ASPECT Super User

MEET THE TEAM

Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies provide humanitarian aid to people affected by disasters. ASPECT provides information on the impact of climate change on disaster risk, helping the British Red Cross to better understand and plan for the impact of climate change on disaster risk.

Dr Elio Mariani
 Director of the Centre for Climate Change Research
 ASPECT Super User

MEET THE TEAM

Save the Children is committed to helping children and young people to thrive. ASPECT provides information on the health and nutritional impacts of climate change on children, helping Save the Children to better understand and plan for the impact of climate change on children's health.

Dr Ravul Pathy
 Director of the Centre for Climate Change Research
 ASPECT Super User

SEASONAL

DECADAL

CLIMATE PROJECTIONS

Agriculture – Grape/wine sector (Codorniu, ES)
 Spring frost protection
 Water management

Finance – Pension sector (Europe)
 Generation & communication of climate risk information for synthetic portfolios

Governance – EU Mission for Climate Adaptation (Emilia-Romagna, IT)
 Strategic climate risk assessment

Disaster response (British Red Cross, UK)
 Response planning during extreme events

Humanitarian – Health and migration (Save the Children International)
 Anticipatory action for malnutrition (child/mother)

CROSS WP COLLABORATION

- internal communication -

Initial consultations

One of the ASPECT objectives: **co-design seamless forecasting systems in close consultation with users.**

The first questionnaire for consultation with internal users was written by WP1 and distributed to the ASPECT work packages in Q1-Q2 2023.

The consultation requested input on:

- enhancements on the forecasting systems configurations and
- archive of variables.

Detailed feedback was received from WPs 3 & 4.

- MS1 'Completion of first round of proposed user-relevant enhancements to seasonal-to-decadal dataset for testing and benchmarking'

WP1 enhancements and relevance from the user and scientist perspectives

You will find below the questionnaire regarding proposed enhancements from WP1 for consultation with the rest of the consortium. There are two main consultation topics: the forecast system configurations and the output requirements. For background on the proposed enhancements, please see the companion document [here](#).

To help us to understand your needs, please also fill this introductory table with your details. There are two categories of users: application and/or climate scientist. Please, fill the one that best describes you.

Table 1: User self-introduction

Application User	
Which application?	
Period for which data are required	
Which sort of data (forecast range)? (seasonal, decadal, projections)	
Variables and data frequency	
Will you use <u>re</u> forecasts only or <u>will also</u> require access to real-time forecasts?	
Other comments	
Climate Scientist	
Which research topic? (blending temporal scales, regional downscaling, verification and process understanding, software and	

Verbal feedback from WPs 4 & 5:

- The questionnaire had **limited utility for reaching Super Users or any 'community of interest' user**, due to the **technical nature** of the questions
- The questionnaire was completed by the **members of WP4** who will use the model outputs for the provision of seamless climate information i.e. members of the community of practice **who create climate services**.
- WP4 identified specific needs for the generation of climate services that can inform the decision-making processes of the Super Users.

Feedback from technical users in WPs 3 & 4:

- A common interest was in the **larger ensemble** size of reforecasts
- Temporal merging requires reforecast periods **as long as possible**
- There was desire for **2-year forecasts**, with at least November and May starts and ensemble size >20
- Downscaling activities require **additional model output on pressure levels in decadal forecasts**, which is not currently available in the decadal repository

Users across the project also checked the **archive of variables** to understand if variables they were likely to need would be provided.

Super User consultations

- **Interviews with all Super Users** led by WP4 Case Study leads
- Super User consultations aim:
 - developing **relationships and trust** with Super User partners
 - to understand **user needs** and **decision making context**
 - developing common understanding on **user perspectives of added value** from seamless predictions
- Activities and material shared with other WPs:
 - Developed '**Protocol for engagement with Super Users**'
 - Developed '**Code of conduct for case study interactions**'
 - Presentations in various WP meetings (WPs 1-3)
 - 'Case study meetings' to ensure Super User needs are understood by the whole consortium
 - Created **Collation of requirements for case studies** from WPs 2 & 3 to help supplement MS13 background, provide hazard specifics and start dialogue on co-production possibilities between WPs 3 & 4
 - Prepared Milestone 13 and Milestone 14 on Provision of requirements of Super Users to WPs 1-3

Super User consultations

In-depth interviews and/or discussion formats allow for flexible, detailed, and bilateral or multilateral (for those involving a group of respondents) conversations between climate service teams and Super Users. Common objectives in terms of what information to gather were set in advance to ensure the consistency of the information collected across the different case studies.

Protocol for interaction with Super Users

- Protocol defines the tasks and topics that will be covered during the first interactions with Super Users
- Interactions will have the objective to understand the Super Users' contexts and identify their information requirements

Code of conduct for case study interactions (CoC)

- CoC is implemented to clarify and facilitate the interactions among ASPECT's partners and Super Users in the context of the work developed for the different case studies
- CoC defines good practice for the smooth development of the project
- Case study leads act as intermediaries between the developers of climate information (WPs 1-3 & 6) and the users of this information
- Technical developments in WPs 1-3 should consider the broader user needs identified in WP5
- Technical developments can be showcased through particular user-targeted activities organised under WPs 5 & 7
- Supplementary table was created for coordination of activities around case studies

WP6 conducted **consultations with other WPs** on produced data, and additional datasets and data types. Based on these consultations Data Management Plan was developed and will be updated regularly during the project lifetime.

The **Data Management Plan** (DMP) describes:

- the data that is produced within the project;
 - how it is shared and where it can be found;
 - how the produced data follows the FAIR data principles; and
 - how partners can contribute their data to the project.
- DMP provides guidelines to make the outputs of the project compatible with the standards used by CDS to ensure that services and relevant datasets developed by the project could be easily considered for inclusion in the C3S at the end of the project.
 - **Documentation** is continually collected through **templates** defined in WP6 and filled in by relevant project partners and WP6
 - **Templates** for the documentation of the ASPECT datasets and the **encoding guidelines** are defined in MS21
- D6.4 Data Management Plan and its updates
- MS21 Encoding guidelines for seasonal forecast data and template of documentation for decadal and 30-year simulations

Internal webinars & case study meetings

Organised to bring together researchers from different WPs to share their work and latest findings, promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange. Presentations and recordings are available on [wiki](#).

Date	Title	Work package
07 March 2024	Met Office Case Study Meeting	WP4
16 May 2024	BSC Case Study Meeting - Agriculture	WP4, WP2 & WP3
03 June 2024	CMCC Case Study Meeting - Governance	WP4
25 June 2024	Met Office Case Study Meeting - Pensions and British Red Cross	WP4
05 July 2024	Current status of the climate simulations and how to access the data	WP1 & WP6
09 July 2024	Climate information use in climate-sensitive organisations in Europe	WP5
26 September 2024	CMCC Case Study Meeting - Governance	WP4, WP2 & WP3
21 October 2024	BSC Case Study Meeting - Agriculture (I part)	WP4 & WP2
12 November 2024	Met Office Case Study Meeting - Pensions and British Red Cross	WP4, WP2 & WP3
18 November 2024	BSC Case Study Meeting - Agriculture (II part)	WP4 & WP3

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Rapid assessment of climate information user needs

Collected user needs from various sources of evidence:

- Review of published literature (peer-reviewed and grey)
- Secondary analysis of C3S's User Requirement: URDB, URAD and Prototype Service for Decadal Climate Predictions
- National Meteorological & Hydrological Service (NMHS) mini-questionnaire
- Initial Super User consultations ([WP4 MS13](#))
- Call for evidence
- Results of the real time surveys (polls) from the first User Forum

Topics of interest:

- Evidence of information use
- Why climate information is(isn't) being used
- Information requirements and other user needs

- [MS17 Presentation of draft D5.1 at first GA to feed into WPs 1,2 & 3](#)
- [D5.1 Rapid assessment of climate information user needs](#)

Rapid assessment of climate information user needs – NMHSs results

- **Community of practice**
- **Seasonal forecast** information widely produced and disseminated by NMHSs
- In some countries used by multiple sectors: transport, energy, water supply, agriculture, tourism, civil protection, etc
- **Barriers** associated with forecast quality and user experience

Forecast quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Lack of reliability.● Lack of accuracy.● Lack of predictive skill/poor skill.● Low verification scores and low confidence.● Low spatial resolution.● The integration of 3 months data has limited use.● Lack of capacity to incorporate the long-timescale probabilistic data into existing decision-making processes, e.g., processes that are designed for week-to-week analysis (based on weather forecasts) can be hard to extend to use a seasonal mean.
User experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● The interpretation of the products can be difficult to understand for novice users.● Users do not know how to use probabilistic forecasts.● Users distrust the forecasts.● Difficult to explain the forecasts to users.● Products not tailored to the users' needs.● Unaware of forecast availability and value.● Economic value of the forecasts is not assessed yet.

Rapid assessment of climate information user needs – NMHSs results

- **Community of practice**
- **Interannual climate forecasts** are produced by 4 NMHSs and 2 NMHSs make them publicly available
- The interest varies across countries and sectors:
 - UK - wind farms
 - DE - forestry and groundwater research
 - SE - several sectors
- **Barriers:**
 - availability, access, and forecast accuracy
 - concerns about the skill level of these forecasts
 - lack of understanding and expertise in calibrating and extracting useful information
 - the need for education and training to maximise their value and integrate them with longer-term climate projections

Rapid assessment of climate information user needs – key findings

- Needs collected both from **Community of interest and community of practice**
- Widespread pattern of **limited use of climate information** across various sectors
- **Barriers** to use consistently identified: perceived low skill and reliability, and non-technical aspects such as ineffective communication and collaboration, limited relevance and usability, lack of capacity and institutional inertia
- **Enablers** supporting use: Established stakeholder relationships and trust, access to resources, tailored and engaging services
- User requirements emphasise the need for **tailored information and data**
- The findings also present contradictions regarding the utilisation of climate information, with some sources indicating limited adoption while others reveal a significant demand. This suggests a **complex landscape** where different sectors may vary in their use and integration of climate information.

Initial findings were presented at first GA to feed into WPs 1-3

Quantitative survey of current climate information use and unmet needs amongst organisations in Europe

All WPs participated in commenting the survey protocol

Translated into 8 languages by project partners

Survey period: October 2023 to January 2024

Data collection:

- Responses collected through sample recruitment company Qualtrics, project partners networks and help of WP7
- Extensive network of participants rewarded for their participation
- Uses techniques to avoid, remove, and replace low-quality responses

Target participants:

- Risk analysts
- Any sector and organisational size

➔ 1864 respondents

Screening questions:

- Organisations sensitive or impacted in some way by weather or climate
- Individuals with at least 1 year of experience

Internal webinar - presentation of user needs (D5.1 and D5.3) to other WPs

- Presentation of analysis from Task 5.3 at second GA/second forum to feed into WPs 1-3
- D5.3 Analysis of how climate information can help organisations prepare for physical changes of a **22** changing climate (in preparation)

Quantitative survey of current climate information use and unmet needs amongst organisations in Europe

Findings from the current users:

- Weather forecast are most frequently used, followed by observations, sub-seasonal and seasonal, with comparatively few participants indicating that they received information for longer timescales.
- **Risks to human safety** and **prior experience** are **key drivers** of climate information use and climate risk management more broadly.

Unmet needs:

- The most commonly selected '**areas for improvement**' are related to **ease of understanding** and **greater accuracy/reliability**.
- This was reflected in perceived **barriers** to climate information use **by interested non-users**, who highlighted a **lack of expertise** and concerns about **accuracy**.
- It is notable that a majority of respondents indicated that their organisation's **planning horizon** for important decisions was **between 1-5 years**, indicating a potential future alignment with interannual prediction timescales.

The second round of consultations

- **Community of practice**
- **When:** Workshop for National Meteorological Services (NMSs, 22-23 October 2024)
- **How:**
 - Presentations and round table discussions
 - During the Workshop, the participants were invited to respond to a short questionnaire.
 - During the Workshop and after, an expanded questionnaire was also circulated among the representatives of the NMSs.
- **Topics** covered their existing practices, hurdles in using the climate data and interest in proposed integrations
- The **results** of the survey showed **strong interest in existing climate information, support for proposed enhancements** as well as obvious **gaps between the level of interest and the level of practical use** of the climate information.
- Substantial work is needed to bridge these gaps, and a way forward would be to **provide more training, discussions and workshops** with NMSs.

➤ MS2 Completion of second round of consultation on proposed user-relevant enhancements to seasonal-to-decadal dataset

Building the community

- **Website**

- Regular updates of articles, events and other sections to inform about the latest project news and updates
- User-centred information on how to get involved, e.g. on User Forums, Super User competition (past content - not available), subscribe to mailing list etc.
- Communication and outreach material to raise awareness about the topics of the project, e.g. paper briefings, infosheets, videos

- **Newsletter**

- Project news and updates sent to mailing list of 250+ contacts

- **Social media presence**

- Regular posts and updates through social media channels (including X, LinkedIn and recently Bluesky)

- **Events**

- Organisation of project events, e.g. User Forums, targetted or open-to-all workshops (e.g. for National Met Service), webinar series etc.
- Participation in external events and conferences to enhance the reach and impact of the project and its results

Building the community

Events

Participation in conferences & relevant events

audience of >2,000-3,000 people attending sessions

- Climateurope2 webstival (Mar '23)
- European Geosciences Union annual meeting in 2023 and 2024
- Oxford Climate Research Network - Annual Conference - Apr '23 & '24
- 6th European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) - Jun '23
- Business Travel Association Planet Plan Conference - Jul '23
- C3S General Assembly - Sep' 23 & Jun '24
- UK Regulators Network Young Professionals Conference event - Sep '23
- Mobile World Congress 2024 (MWC24) - Feb '24
- Climateurope2 Festival - Mar '24
- Event on 'Collaborating for Impact: Bridging the Gap Between Climate Science and Insurance Industry Practice' - Mar '24
- NCAR Workshop on Predictability across time scales - Apr '24
- River Basin conference (CLIMAX-PO) - Apr '24
- Workshop on Climate Prediction and Services over the Atlantic-Arctic region, Bergen - May '24
- Local event on climate change and drought in Catalonia - May '24
- 15th International Meeting on Statistical Climatology (IMSC) - Jun '24

Interactions with:

- community of interest
- community of practice
- scientific community

USER ENGAGEMENT

- events -

Annual multi-sector user fora: a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users

The background

- **Online** sessions organised annually by the ASPECT project, offering a **collaborative space** to share knowledge, experiences, and challenges related to climate predictions and services for decision making related to climate adaptation.
- Forums are designed to **bring together** climate researchers, providers and users of climate services, and other interested organisations from a range of sectors across society interested in learning how to effectively use climate information within their organisation.
- Forums provide a unique opportunity to explore user requirements and use cases and enhance the overall usability of climate predictions.

The primary objectives of the multi-sector User Forums include the following:

- **Provide a platform for collaboration** by facilitating effective interactions and fostering exchange between the ASPECT consortium and various climate information users and other stakeholders.
- **Promote a deeper understanding** of how climate information and knowledge can assist organisations in preparing for and adapting to a changing climate. This involve gathering insights on the practical application of climate forecast information and identifying potential barriers that constrain its use.
- **Promote** the use of climate predictions in society.
- **Explore the feasibility of scaling up** the use of climate predictions and determine the necessary steps to do so.
- **Disseminate knowledge and information** about climate prediction to a wider audience.
- **Build a community of practice** regarding the use of climate predictions.

Annual multi-sector user fora: a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users

The first User Forum

- Took place on 24 March and 21 April 2023 as a two-session event.
- **First session:**
 - Guest event during the first Climeurope2 webstival
 - Registered 242, participated 99
 - Introduction to the project, perspectives from a Super User and private sector information provider
 - **Dialogues** between users and producers of seamless climate information
 - Launching a **call for expression of interest** for becoming a Super User
 - Mentimeter **survey** (85 participants)
 - To better understand the audience perspective, needs and how ASPECT can support climate information needs.
 - The **reasons for using climate information**: climate services, early warning, informed decisions, research, adaptation, and prediction.
 - **Enablers** mentioned were: public tools, metadata, and visualisations.
 - **Barriers** included: complexity, understanding, and uncertainty.
 - **Varied preferences for climate prediction lead times**, with 10 years being the most useful, followed by 30 years, 3 months, and 5 years.
 - Results described in [D5.1 Rapid assessment of climate information user need](#)

Annual multi-sector user fora: a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users

The first User Forum

- **Second session:**
 - Registered 38, participated 23
 - More detailed information on technical modelling frameworks and the requirements for applying predictions
 - **Potential Super Users** shared a series of use cases that they have developed as part of their application
 - **Breakout group discussions** where participants shared their experiences with climate predictions and explored how ASPECT's data could enhance their activities
 - One group focused on ASPECT's contribution to the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and the involvement of regional authorities and agencies from the regions enrolled in the Mission.
 - The second breakout group discussed climate service providers who can leverage cutting-edge climate predictions through innovative applications.
 - The other group engaged both the providers of climate services and the end users. The discussion revolved around topics such as timing and rules of engagement, as well as the benefits for the users' organizations.
- **Video recordings** of both sessions available on ASPECT webpage:

<https://www.aspect-project.eu/user-forums/>

Annual multi-sector user fora: a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users

The second User Forum

- Took place from 30. January to 01. February 2024 as 3-day/session event
- registered 234, participated 168
- **First session:**
 - Focused on raising awareness and promoting a deeper understanding of seamless climate forecasts
 - Presentation of two Super Users
 - Experienced users discussed why climate predictions matter and how climate information helps with decision making
- **Second session:**
 - Highlight of ASPECT research and innovation
 - Announcement and introduction of **new Super Users**
 - Presentation of preliminary analysis of user needs from Task 5.3 (**MS18**)
- **Third session:** focused on one-on-one or small group discussions between ASPECT scientists and current and potential users who want to dive deeper into the potential use of seasonal to decadal climate information
- **Video recordings** of sessions available on ASPECT webpage:
<https://www.aspect-project.eu/user-forums/>

A promotional graphic for the ASPECT User Forum 2024. The background is dark green with orange and white accents. On the left, it says "ASPECT" at the top, followed by "USER FORUM 2024" in large, bold, orange and white letters. Below that, it reads "ADVANCING CLIMATE ADAPTATION WITH SEAMLESS AND TAILORED CLIMATE PREDICTIONS". At the bottom left, it shows the dates "30 JAN to 01 FEB 2024" and a QR code with the word "Register" below it. On the right, there is a circular image of wind turbines in a field. Text next to the image says "ASPECT's second annual user forum, connecting climate researchers and users across Europe". Below that, it explains that ASPECT is at the forefront of climate prediction capabilities and that the forum is an opportunity for climate-resilient organizations to learn about the latest developments in climate prediction science and share their experiences. At the bottom right, it asks "Who can join?" and states that the forum is open to anyone interested in understanding climate predictions and how they can be applied to decision-making, including current or potential users of climate information, representatives from a public agency, business owners, or members of non-governmental organisations. The website "www.aspect-project.eu" is at the bottom right.

Annual multi-sector user fora: a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users

The second User Forum

- Imbalanced participation between days, with almost twice as many participants in the first day
- Participation mainly from the UK, Italy, and Spain; low engagement from Central and Eastern Europe
- Retention issues: 20% of second forum attendees were also at the first.
- Difficulty in obtaining feedback: only a 10% response rate to post-event surveys
- Sessions should be limited the sessions to 2 hours
- There is a need for better organisation of bilateral meetings
- Improved accessibility and suggested different sessions for novice vs. experienced users to improve retention

Efforts will be made to overcome these issues in the Third User Forum

Workshop for NMSs

Targeted event for community of practice

- National Meteorological Services (NMSs)
- Engaging with NMSs aims to:
 - Inform the WPs1-3 on user needs and challenges,
 - Complement the Super Users in WP4,
 - Supplement information gained during User Forums in WP5,
 - Help upscaling activities in WP5,
 - Inform the design of workflows and applications developed by WP6,
 - Help further uptake of ASPECT outputs and exploitation activities in WP7,
 - Enable lasting impact of the ASPECT project.
- Workshop
 - Aimed to enhance communication, showcase ASPECT research, gather feedback, and establish channels for sharing climate prediction data
 - Took place: 22-23 October 2024, online
 - Registered 146 (44 countries), participated 118 (40 countries) from NMSs
 - It featured a set of presentations and extensive discussions

Number of registered participants from NMSs

Number of participants from NMSs

Workshop for NMSs

Targeted event for community of practice

Workshop highlights:

- Assessing the value of initialization in climate predictions is important.
 - Modes of variability except ENSO and their interactions remain areas for further research.
 - Addressing model deficiencies, such as signal-to-noise issues and predictable components, is crucial.
 - The effectiveness of downscaling techniques depends on the quality, resolution, and length of available observational data for training and calibration.
 - Testing new methods is difficult due to the limited high-quality observational data, as well as number of cases and initialization dates of traditional simulations.
 - Many users are often unaware of, struggle to understand or have difficulty distinguishing between interannual climate predictions and long-term projections.
 - Users prioritize credibility, clarity, and relevance over the source of the data, whether it comes from predictions or projections.
 - Many services and tools start as prototypes funded by research projects, and maintaining and transitioning them into operational practice is challenging.
 - A profitable market for climate services is hard to identify.
 - Translating predictions into tangible value, like economic savings and cost-benefit contexts, was proposed.
 - There are gaps in education for interpreting and communicating seasonal and climate predictions.
- MS26 Review of participation in RCOF events and engagement with National Met Services, summarise progress to date and ongoing strategy

IMPACT ON PREDICTION SYSTEM DEVELOPMENTS

What do we know users want?

“Forecast skill [of interannual climate predictions] is even lower than for seasonal forecasts”

Community of practice on why they are not using interannual climate predictions

From the surveys, Super User engagement, and general user engagement by consortium partners which complements specific ASPECT activity we know...

Community of interest: The “best information”, “just one number/timeseries!”

Community of practice (at a range of technical levels):

For local applications and rainfall extremes – High resolution data – ideally at same resolution as highest climate projection models available, i.e. convecting permitting resolution.

For extremes – Hourly and daily resolution data

For regional downscaling – multiple level output, not just surface variables.

For temporal merging – long reforecasts, lots of different start dates (typically prediction systems only start twice a year in November and May) and 1-2 year predictions

All variables including earth system models – e.g. soil moisture for agricultural applications

More ensemble members – better signal-to-noise ratio, skill, understanding uncertainty

Better models! – that better represent observed earth system processes and climate sensitivity.

Integration of **user needs** and facilitating **knowledge exchange** within and external to the consortium to ensure:

- **climate information** and **technical/scientific methods are tailored** to the Super User's requirements
- **upscaling** to a broader community of stakeholders
- **empowerment for decision making around adaptation** that can be repeated by other users in **other locations** and across **different sectors**

WP1

- **Wide possibility of future potential needs** from a range of users should be balanced appropriately with the limited range of possible direct user interactions within the project, as well as taking in additional considerations such as **computational cost** and **data volume**.
- Proposed a variety of **proposed enhancements** at the beginning of the project
- Enhancements are based on many years and experience of many consortium members, from world leading prediction centres, which gain wide insight from a range of user needs through their wider work and that of their colleagues who focus on user engagement at these institutions. Therefore, they already have **been implicitly informed by user engagement** by these modelling centres in the past.

Prediction System Developments

Integration of **user needs** and facilitating **knowledge exchange** within and external to the consortium to ensure:

- **climate information** and **technical/scientific methods are tailored** to the Super User's requirements
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WP2

- Collaboration with other WPs on the design of prediction system developments to ensure that methods and **products are tailored** to the needs of the users.
- Continued skill assessment of seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions for the **improved interpretation** of climate predictions and the origins of the predictive skill.
- Preparation of **guidelines** on how to assess skill in seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions for the research community and the communication with the users.

Integration of **user needs** and facilitating **knowledge exchange** within and external to the consortium to ensure:

- **climate information** and **technical/scientific methods are tailored** to the Super User's requirements
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WP3–WP4 communication

- Ensures **usable products** by conveying necessary **information** on
 - potential and needs of scientific methods
 - needs of Super Users
- Conclusions on:
 - **geographical regions** of interest
 - **key variables**
 - relevant type of **extreme** events
 - **design** of science-technical methods for usable products
- Initially, focus on Catalonia agricultural case and Emilia Romagna “governance” case
- Increasing activities for “red cross” use case

Objective 6

Design & implement a delivery system for the data and methods produced by ASPECT, enabling the scaling up of the use of climate risk information on the 1-30-year time scale beyond pilot studies.

Initial steps towards a delivery system

- Created and keeping up to date Data Management Plan
- New project datasets and their documentation stored in ESGF and MARS to ensure wider accessibility
- Online catalogue with decadal forecasts

ASPECT Documentation

Created by Charalambos Karvelis, last modified on Apr 26, 2024

- 1. Introduction
- 2. Seasonal prediction
- 3. Extended seasonal prediction
- 4. Decadal - Extended decadal prediction
- 5. 30-year outlooks
- 6. Historical - Projections
- 7. Other data types

ASPECT: Datasets documentation

1. Introduction

The ASPECT (Adaptation-oriented Seamless Predictions of European Climate) project produces tailored to support improved resilience to future climate and weather. The project is delivered by projection and impacts) and social science (user engagement, climate services, communication)

ASPECT sets up and demonstrates a seamless climate information system with a time horizon of sectoral applications. The goal is to improve existing prediction systems and merge their outputs standard for sectoral decision-making.

ASPECT is designed around seven work packages (WPs). WPs 1 to 3 provide the climate forecasts downscaling approaches and identification of extremes. WPs 4 to 7 form a cluster that focuses on engaging with the users, delivering data, methods and guidance to drive and inform adaptation, as well as wider communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

ASPECT documentation contains a list of the datasets, the models and the experiments, a definition of variables and frequencies, details on where to find the data, how to access and download the data, possible issues with the data, etc.

Data documentation is a continuous process throughout the project and it's a live document that will be updated regularly.

2. Seasonal prediction

Decadal forecasts give a prediction on the probability that the climate system will be warmer, drier, wetter or cooler than the long-term average for that time of year and to be based on seasonal climate forecasts.

Catalogue with graphical results

For easier **cross-WP** information sharing of what is done in WPs 1-3 and **support discussions with Super Users**.

Online catalogue of decadal prediction graphical products

- Shiny application in R (web application);
- Support systematic monitoring of the new simulations;
- Include selected forecast quality metrics

ASPECT **Shiny App** consists of:

- Forecast quality including maps of the skill metrics
- Forecasts maps including maps of the ensemble mean anomaly and most likely tercile
- Documentation

https://earth.bsc.es/shiny/cdelgado_ASPECT-WP6-M22/

Workflow & Application

Aimed at the general public with an interest in weather/climate;
not aimed at scientists trying to download datasets

- Implemented **React-redux** among other technologies - state management framework to **enable the user to interact with the website**

- **Advertise the power of the product to a wider audience**

- Must be responsive, i.e. make a plot within 2s

- 60% of internet traffic is on mobile, so must work equally well on mobile or desktop

- Must be built in a modular way so we can reuse components and also ensure consistency across C3S/ECMWF apps etc

- Development under **analysis**:
 - Initially using CDS data and gradually ASPECT integrations, initial discussions on how to integrate:
 - the temporal merging of multi-annual to seasonal forecasts/decadal to multi-decadal (WP3)
 - the downscaling of forecasts (WP3)
 - seasonal to multi-annual predictions of extremes (WP2)
 - applications to illustrate the use of different type of predictions (WPs 4 and 5)
- Conducted various trainings in different technical aspects relevant to ASPECT science applications (Javascript React, Helm, Github Actions, Kubernetes, Docker)

Delivery of data

Enhanced documentation

WP6 give **guidance** to project partners **on how to access and download the new data**

WP6 has produced ASPECT documentation, a collection of web pages of the new simulations as well as the existing data used by the project.

The documentation includes information on

- where to find the simulations and data;
- access to the description of model simulations
- other relevant aspects, such as the experimental design, the list of variables, etc

Documentation is:

- hosted by ECMWF confluence as a set of webpages and will be updated regularly
- available to project partners

Description of the ASPECT forecast systems

This table shows the centres that provide data to this project together with the latest configuration of their systems. Follow the link of each Data Pro description.

Status on	Time range (forecasts and hindcasts)	Forecast initial conditions	Forecast ensemble size	Hindcast initial conditions	Hindcast ensemble size	Hindcast period
08 Mar 2024						
BSC EC3 Lowres	36 months			1st of May/Nov	20	May init: 1960-2021 Nov init: 1960-2021
BSC EC3 Highres	36 months			1st of May/Nov	15	May in: Nov in:
ECMWF SEAS5 Lowres CER3-20C	24 months	-	-	1st of May/Nov	10	1960-1
ECMWF SEAS5 24-month integrations	24 months	-	-	1st of May/Nov	25	1961-1
ECMWF SEAS6	24 months	-	-	1st of May/Nov	20	1960-

Variable Longname (DCPP description)	IFS/GRIB name	IFS/GRIB units	CMIP/CMOR variable short name	CMIP/CMOR Units	Mapping with IFS variable	Frequencies		Note
						IFS/REASS	DCPP	
TDA fluxes								
TDA Incident Shortwave Radiation (solar incident)	1st (21)	J m ⁻² down	radl	W m ⁻² down	source grb212 = target 'radl' unless IFS high-frequency convert: cur23sat factor = 1.0 / (3600 * output_frequency) term = 0.0	24h accumulation / mon	mon	
TDA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation (solar out)	1st (17)	grb1776: J m ⁻² down grb212: J m ⁻² down	radl	W m ⁻² up	source (long: grb1776-grb212) = target 'radl' unless IFS high-frequency convert: cur23sat factor = 1.0 / (3600 * output_frequency) term = 0.0	24h accumulation / mon	mon	
					en IFS months mean: rms_factor_units = null IFS units = W m ⁻²			
					en IFS months mean: rms_factor_units = null IFS units = W m ⁻²			
					en IFS high-frequency convert: cur23sat term = 0.0			
					en IFS months mean: rms_factor_units = null IFS units = W m ⁻²			
					en IFS high-frequency convert: cur23sat term = 0.0			
					en IFS months mean: rms_factor_units = null IFS units = W m ⁻²			
					en IFS high-frequency convert: cur23sat term = 0.0			

- Forecast system version
- Configuration of the forecast model
 - 2.1 Atmosphere and land surface
 - 2.2 Ocean and cryosphere
- Boundary conditions - climate forcings
 - 4.1 Atmosphere and land
 - 4.2 Ocean and cryosphere
- Model Uncertainties perturbations:
- Forecast system and hindcasts
 - Horizontal interpolation
 - Vertical interpolation
- Other relevant information

Delivery of data & information

How are model data being delivered to potential users?

- Organised data delivery system with guidance/documentation and user support
- Using existing data platforms:
 - Seasonal (CDS, MARS)
 - Decadal (ESGF)

Using similar strategies with CDS

- data catalogue' menu on the ASPECT website

WP4 created initial suggestions for an accessible **FAQ** addressing user relevant queries on the ASPECT web page. All WPs will cooperate in creating the question list and providing the content

WP3 are proposing to provide information about **ensemble sub-subsets** using .yaml format

A screenshot of the Copernicus Data Catalogue interface. At the top, there are search filters for 'Search datasets', 'Sector', 'Region', and 'Data provider'. Below the filters, three data product cards are displayed. The first card is titled 'ERA5 hourly climate and weather data from 1940 to present' and includes a world map. The second card is titled 'European energy and climate data explorer' and includes a map of Europe and a line graph. The third card is titled 'Global ocean physics analysis and forecast' and includes a map of the ocean.

To access the Copernicus Security Service (CSS) products please contact copernicus@satcen.europa.eu

Data providers

- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)
- Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CMS)
- Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS)
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS)
- Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)
- Copernicus Security Service (CSS)

Identified challenges in user engagement

- It is time consuming to understand **decision making processes** for a sector and Super User, which is vital to building decision useful climate services.
- Some mismatch in **expectations** between **specifics** requested from Super Users by WPs 1-3 and the decision making context of most Super Users and how climate information is used by many users, and the co-production time taken to develop the case studies by WP4.
- **Downscaling** of climate predictions to the user needs
- **Upscaling**: expansion of downscaling method developments to other European regions for broader user engagement
- **Combining information** from downscaling and time merging for users
- **Surveying user needs** - cannot be reliably used to explore the needs of specific cases in depth
- Motivate the people to attend all sessions of User Forums and achieve more geographical diversity of participants

PLANS FOR THE NEXT PERIOD

Plans for the next period

WP1

- Increase the attendance of WP1's partners to the user-related activities
- Assist WP6 with the data portal, to ensure the data is documented
- Interact with and support the other WPs

WP2

- **Continued** collaboration with other WPs and the Super Users to determine and deliver useful information from seamless predictions.
- Advancement of multi-system skill assessments of novel forecast horizons (in cooperation with WP1).

WP3

- **Continued** collaboration with WP4 to ensure that methods and **products are tailored** to the needs of the Super Users.
- To co-design and develop a **temporally merged product for the Red Cross heat wave case study**, possibly upscalable to other European regions

Plans for the next period

WP4

- Case study leads are in regular contact with Super Users to support WP4 activity
- **Design climate service prototypes** in co-production with Super Users.
- Define 'good practices' for the delivery of model-based climate data and services (use outcomes of Super User interactions + team-up with WP5 to assess the opinions of additional users. Results will be input for WP6).
- Assess the value of climate services for Super Users and the added value of seamless climate information.

WP5

- Continue to facilitate the cooperation and interactions of WPs during User Engagement Committee meetings in order to enhance interaction with users
- Continue to facilitate the interactions between ASPECT scientists and users through annual multi-sector User Fora
- Explore the extent to which products and communication strategies tailored to specific use cases can be upscaled to a wider range of users through survey-based experiments
- Helping inform whether delivery system as well as application/workflow developed in WP6 are going to meet user requirements

Plans for the next period

WP6

- Continue the discussion with WPs 3-5 for the co-development of a series of workflows
- Selected workflows will be released publicly provided that all the tests have been passed using operational settings
- Deliver the online catalogue of decadal prediction graphical products
- WP6 will regularly meet with WPs 3 & 4 to discuss data management needs (e.g. encoding of downscaled products, or other derived products), as well as to discuss the socioeconomic data that will be used in ASPECT (WPs 4 & 5)

WP7

- Nurture the communities of users during the project (e.g. User Forums and Workshops) and ensure these communities last after the project end (e.g. Climate Information Delivery System)
- Release of new dissemination material for community of interest (educational material, infosheets, infographics etc.)
- Support other WPs in organising targeted events, workshops and webinars
- Organise trainings to potential new users of S2D predictions in cooperation with other WPs
- Exploitation activities: delivering digital handbook and other supporting materials, as well as engagement with NMSs for further uptake of ASPECT results

Annual multi-sector user fora: a space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users

The third User Forum (in preparation)

- **Pre-event:**
 - Regional Dialogue on Seamless Climate Prediction – ITALY
 - 11/02/2025, at the first day of General Assembly
 - Engagement with regional communities of interest and practice
- **Event:**
 - 25-27 March 2025, online
 - Session 1: Dedicated to community of interest
 - Session 2: Dedicated to community of practice
 - Session 3: Bilateral discussions or Marketplace for climate prediction products

International workshop on seamless predictions

- International 2-day workshop on seamless predictions from interannual to multi-decadal timescales (1–30 years) with a focus on understanding, including the following themes:
 - origins of predictability and drivers of climate variations;
 - deficiencies of predicting systems impacting forecast quality;
 - challenges in predicting extremes.
- When: **Autumn 2025**
- Where: **Bologna, Italy**
- Co-organization with other EU projects and exploring links with DCPD and EPESC
- Engaging with the **scientific community**

CONTACT

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Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101081460. The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the ASPECT project and does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.